

MULTITHREADING FOR VIDEO PROCESSING APPLICATIONS RUNNING ON PC WORKSTATIONS

Eric Debes, Fulvio Moschetti

Signal Processing Laboratory, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology,
CH-1015 Lausanne SWITZERLAND

Tel: +41 21 693 47 09, fax: +41 21 693 76 00

e-mail: eric.debes@epfl.ch, fulvio.moschetti@epfl.ch

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to show how an efficient exploitation of the multithreading technique can speed up video applications running on PC Workstations. We show how to use multithreading for pure processing in order to exploit the full computational power of multiprocessor machines. Different multithreading techniques are compared and the efficiency of multithreading is discussed. It is explained why multithreading can be a very helpful technique to avoid CPU idle state while reading and writing video to disk or displaying video on the screen. Disk reading is chosen as an example to give the gain that can be obtained using multithreading for input/output operations. Finally it is shown how multithreading can be used to take advantage of the external processing power available in graphic cards or acquisition boards. Indeed, very often in video processing applications, some routines can be done in hardware while another thread is running in parallel in order to keep the main CPU busy.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, more and more PC Workstations have two or more processors. If an application is not multithreaded, it cannot use the full processing power of these machines. In fact, if just one single-threaded application runs on a dual CPU machine, only half of the processing power is used and the rest is wasted. We show in the next part that multithreading can be a very efficient technique to take advantage of the many CPUs available in multiprocessor machines.

Another aspect that is considered relies on the ever growing speed of CPUs even though input/output flow does not really keep up with them in the same way. Therefore, very often, the most difficult issue in video applications is not to process data, but to keep the CPUs busy through providing them enough data to process. Indeed, in most video applications, CPUs are often in idle state waiting for new data to be processed or for data to be written back to the disk or displayed on the screen. We show that multithreading makes it possible to avoid CPU idle state in these cases.

Finally, today many PC Workstations are equipped with dedicated processors for specific tasks. This is especially the case for graphic cards and acquisition boards that integrate more and more functionalities in hardware. We explain how multithreading can be used to take advantage of this external processing power. Some routines can be executed in hardware chips while another thread is running in parallel to keep the main CPU busy.

2 MULTITHREADING FOR VIDEO PROCESSING ON MULTIPROCESSOR SYSTEMS

2.1 Different Multithreading Techniques and Thread Management

Multithreading techniques can be very different depending on the operating system used. As Microsoft Windows has become the main platform for video processing applications, we restrict our study to this group of operating systems. Similar multithreading techniques can be applied to other operating systems like Linux thanks to Posix Threads [1] for example. The different multithreading techniques explained in this section are mainly specific to Windows NT, but can be easily extended to other operating systems.

In Windows NT and Windows 2000, the thread is the basic unit of execution and a process can contain multiple, independent threads sharing the process's address space and other resources. In this section, we present two multithreading techniques under Microsoft Windows NT operating system. Interested readers can find more detailed information on this topic in [2][3]. The first and easiest technique consists in creating a thread each time a function has to be executed in parallel with the main thread. This can be done under Windows NT using the function `CreateThread` that returns a handle to the thread. When the thread function returns, one just have to close the handle to kill the thread. But very often in real multimedia applications, the same function is run many times consecutively with different input parameters. In this case creating and destroying a thread for each execution is a waste of time. Indeed using the

Figure 1: Gain for Classical Method

Figure 2: Gain for Event-based Method

Intel instruction "rdtsc" [4], it is possible to measure that the creation and the destruction of a thread takes nearly $M_C = 50.000$ cycles. A "lighter" solution consists in using Events. In this case the processing thread is created just once at the beginning of the application, and Events are used to send messages to this thread in order to run or to stop it. Therefore thread management is much lower and takes just $M_E = 5.000$ cycles. This technique is especially well suited for video processing applications in which the same functions are executed very often for different data.

2.2 Thread Management and Minimum Size of Tasks to be Multithreaded

When a function is multithreaded a good approximation of the gain for the execution speed is :

$$G = \frac{T}{\frac{T}{N} + M_i} \quad (1)$$

where G is the gain for this function, T is the time needed without multithreading, N is the number of processors available and M_i is the management time with $i = C$ for the classical multithreading method and $i = E$ for the Event-based method. Assuming it is worth multithreading if the gain is at least 1.5 on a dual CPU machine, T should be larger than $6M_i$ according to eq. 1. This means that the smallest executing time of a function to be multithreaded should be $6M_C$ cycles if the classical multithreading method is used and $6M_E$ cycles if the Event-based method is used.

We tested this model for a subtraction between two matrices (actually two image parts). Knowing that the subtraction of two elements takes in average 1 cycle (including reading and writing to memory), according to the model the size of the matrix should be at least $6M_i$ elements. The application tells us that the gain 1.5 is obtained for a matrix of size 300.000 pixels for the classical thread method and 25.000 pixels for the event-based method (fig. 1 and fig. 2). This experiment confirms the model.

2.3 Number of threads to be created in video processing applications

Motion estimation is the major computational bottleneck of many video encoders. It has been multithreaded in an MPEG2 encoder by creating N threads (N ranging from 1 to 60), each of which is executing the motion estimation on 1/Nth of the frame. The results of this experiment show that it is not worth creating more threads than the number of processors available. Indeed creating more threads just creates an overhead due to thread management. Actually, with this experiment we also measured the time needed for thread management. Results obtained confirm that classical thread management takes M_C cycles and that the event based thread management takes M_E cycles.

However, usually video processing algorithms are linear algorithms, with different successive tasks, which can very often take advantage of multithreading even if tasks are very small. The well known Amdahl's law [5] gives the gain G depending on the fraction of time F spent in the multithreaded code and the number of processor N:

$$G = \frac{1}{1 - F + \frac{F}{N}} \quad (2)$$

This formula shows that F should be as high as possible. On the other hand, we have seen in section 2.2 that a task is worth multithreading with the Event-based method if it lasts at least $6M_E$ cycles. Therefore, as a rule of thumb all functions which last more than $6M_E$ cycles (0,1ms on a 300MHz system) should be multithreaded by creating for each function a number of threads equal to the number of processors available, regardless the total number of threads created for the complete application. In real-life applications, multithreading gives a very interesting gain if many functions are multithreaded.

For example, we have been multithreading many functions (motion estimation, DCT, inverse DCT, quantization, inverse quantization, etc) in the Software Simulation Group MPEG2 encoder [6] and the overall gain

Figure 3: gain obtained after multithreading on a 4-way Pentium Pro

of the application is higher than 1.8 on a dual CPU machine, which is a very encouraging result for such a linear application. Moreover it also scales if the number of processors is higher than two. A version of the encoder without the MMX optimization was tested on a 4-way Pentium Pro Server. The results given in fig. 3 show that our implementation of the MPEG2 encoder can really take advantage of 4 processors and that the gain using 1, 2 and 4 processors is nearly linear.

3 Multithreading for Video Input/Output

In the current trend, CPU speed increases faster than I/O flow. Therefore, to achieve good performance it is vital to avoid any possible CPU idle time especially when many data are processed, written to or read from a disk or displayed on a screen. In this case again, multithreading can help. Let's take for example the problem of disk reading for video encoding. If new frames are only loaded when new data are needed, i.e. at the beginning of the encoding process, CPUs are idling during the whole loading of the frame.

To load frames of volume $V = width \times height \times B$ bits, at a frame rate of FR frames/s, if the disk reading speed is RS , the time needed to load enough frames for real-time encoding, is :

$$T = V \times \frac{FR}{RS} \quad (3)$$

For example, if we target real-time MPEG2 encoding in CIF (width=352, height=288) YUV 4:2:0 (B=12 bits per pixel) format at 25 frames per second on a system with disk reading at a speed of 40Mbit/s,

$$T = 352 \times 288 \times 12 \times \frac{25}{40 \cdot 10^6} = 0.76s. \quad (4)$$

If this task is not done in parallel with the encoding process, just 25% of the time is free for processing and encoding frames.

Therefore frame reading can be considered as one of the main bottlenecks in the encoding process if this task

is not multithreaded. If the reading of the different frames can be done in parallel, the total execution time can be speed up. If the average processing time for one frame is APT , the speed up factor is:

$$G = \frac{APT + \frac{V}{RS}}{APT} \quad (5)$$

For example, with $APT = 0.1s$ (10 frames processed per second), $V = 1.2Mbit$ and $RS = 40Mbit/s$,

$$G = \frac{0.1 + \frac{1.2}{40}}{0.1} = 1.3 \quad (6)$$

so that the encoder is running 30% faster if the frame reading is done in parallel with the processing tasks. It is assumed that the CPU use of file reading can be neglected. This technique has been implemented in an MPEG4 encoder using the Microsoft reference software. In our implementation, the next frame to be processed is loaded while the current frame is encoded. For an encoding rate of 7 frames per second for CIF format, the gain obtained thanks to the multithreading of file reading ranges from 20% up to 50% depending on the CPU speed of the system used and on the disk reading speed. Indeed if the disk is slow and the CPU is fast, the relative time spent reading files from the disk will be higher than for a system with a faster disk and a slower CPU. Therefore the results of this technique are very much hardware dependent.

The example of reading images from a disk shows how the exploitation of multithreading can be useful for hiding the latency due to input and output operations. The same technique can be applied to other I/O operations. For example for a video player, one thread can take care of decoding the bit stream while another thread displays the decoded frame on the screen. This makes it possible to speed up the decoding process, because the decoding thread does not have to wait till the frame is copied to the video memory before starting the decoding of the next frame.

This kind of technique is in fact quite general and should be applied to any I/O operation in order to hide the latency due to the speed difference between the I/O devices and the main processor.

4 Multithreading for External Processing

Video processing algorithms are very demanding and even if processors are becoming very powerful today, the complexity of the applications is increasing rapidly and thus video processing and video encoding applications cannot very often run in real time on a general purpose processor. Moreover, graphic cards and acquisition boards integrate more and more functionalities in hardware. Multithreading can be used to take advantage of this external processing power by executing some routines in hardware chips in parallel with other functions running on the CPU. Under Windows 2000, this

can be done using DirectX [7] to get access to hardware functionalities. To do so, a new COM filter [8] has to be designed and integrated in an existing DirectX Media flow graph [9]. For example commonly available MPEG2 decoders give the results in YUV 4:2:0 color space, and then an additional YUV to RGB conversion needs to be executed in order to display the image on the screen. But today, most graphic cards can do this conversion in hardware, so that it is not necessary to use the main CPU for this task. Moreover, many graphic cards integrate some other crucial functions for video decoding like the inverse discrete cosine transform and even sometimes the motion compensation. The exploitation of all these hardware functions makes it possible to obtain a real time MPEG2 player without overloading the main processor. Indeed, if we can assume that the hardware executed functions can be run in parallel with the rest of the software, the speed gain can be expressed by:

$$G = \frac{1}{1 - F} \quad (7)$$

where F is the fraction of the code which is executed in the external processor.

This technique has been implemented on an MPEG2 player based on the original code from the Software Simulation Group on a HP Kayak equipped with an ATI Rage Pro graphic card under Microsoft Windows 2000 Professional with DirectX7.0. The result is that the player is running 60% faster if the conversion YUV to RGB is done in hardware.

This type of multithreading technique can also be very interesting for the exploitation of 3D graphic and OpenGL acceleration capacities of hardware chips available in most graphic cards today. When a 3D scene has to be rendered, the first part of the decoding can be done by the main processor. The rest can be executed directly in the 3D chips on the graphic card through the exploitation of the OpenGL libraries which can be executed by a dedicated processor on the graphic card.

This technique makes it possible to exploit the power of dedicated processors on graphic cards, but also the video memory which is becoming more and more important on the latest graphic cards. This memory is faster than classical RAM. In addition when a function is executed in the dedicated chip, the main bus (CPU-RAM) is not overloaded, because the dedicated processor is mainly accessing just data in the video memory which is on the graphic card.

The exploitation of multithreading for external processing is not interesting just for graphic cards, but it can also be very useful for acquisition and dedicated DSP boards. Indeed, today video acquisition cards integrate also many processors for pre-processing, for format conversion or even for encoding (e.g. Motion JPEG encoding). Through the use of multithreading, these functionalities can be exploited while some other functions run in parallel on the main CPU. It is also possible to

use PCI boards integrating dedicated or general purpose DSPs like for example the VLIW chips TriMedia from Philips Semiconductors [10]. Intensive functions can be executed in the DSP while the rest of the application can run on the main PC processor through creating different threads for the most computation demanding functions.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we have shown that multithreading can be a very useful technique to write efficient video processing applications for PC Workstations. Multithreading allows not only to exploit the different processors available in these systems, but also to avoid CPU idle time during input/output operations and to execute some functions in hardware chips available in graphic and acquisition cards. The full exploitation of this technique very often makes it possible to run some very demanding video processing applications in real time on PC Workstations instead of using very expensive dedicated hardware.

References

- [1] David R. Butenhof, Programming with POSIX Threads, Addison-Wesley Professional Computing Series, 1997.
- [2] M. Brain, Win32 System Services, Chapter 5, Prentice Hall, 1996.
- [3] J. M. Hart, Win32 System Programming, Chapter 10, Addison-Wesley Advanced Windows Series, 1997.
- [4] Intel , "Using the RDTSC Instruction for Performance Monitoring" Intel Developer Web Site Applications Notes : <http://developer.intel.com/drg/pentiumii/app-notes/RDTSCPM1.HTM>
- [5] G. Amdahl, "Validity of the Single-Processor Approach to Achieving Large-Scale Computing Capabilities", Proc. 1967 AFIPS Conf. Vol. 30, P483.
- [6] MPEG Software Simulation Group MPEG2 encoder, <http://www.mpeg.org/MPEG/MSSG/>
- [7] B. Bargaen, P. Donnelly, "Inside DirectX", Microsoft Programming Series, Microsoft Press, Redmond, Washington, 1998.
- [8] C. Corry, V. W. Mayfield, J. Cadman, R. C. Morin, "COM/DCOM Primer Plus", Sams Publishing, 1999.
- [9] Microsoft DirectXMedia Web Site, <http://www.microsoft.com/directx/dxm>
- [10] Philips Semiconductors TriMedia Web Site, <http://www.semiconductors.philips.com/trimedia>